

The Effect of Music on National Athletes' Training

Milli Sporcuların Antrenmanlarına Müziğin Etkisi

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the effects of music on the training processes of national athletes. A total of 544 national athletes from various sports disciplines voluntarily participated in this study. Data were collected using the "Impact of Music on the Sportive Activities Scale" (IMSAS), which evaluates three sub-dimensions: motivation, psychological resilience, and physical strength/performance. Statistical analyses were conducted via SPSS 25.0, including independent sample t-tests and one-way ANOVA. The results revealed that music positively influences athletes' motivation, enhances physical performance, and strengthens psychological resilience during training. Notably, female athletes, younger age groups (18–22), those with 1–3 years of sports experience, athletes with higher education and socioeconomic status, and those engaged in team sports benefited more from music-supported training sessions. The findings highlight the importance of personalized music integration into training programs, emphasizing that the impact of music varies according to individual differences. This study contributes to the growing literature in sports psychology and exercise science by emphasizing music as a valuable tool to optimize athletic performance and mental preparedness.

Keywords: Music, National Athletes, Training, Motivation

Özet

Bu araştırma, müziğin millî sporcuların antrenman süreçlerine olan etkilerini incelemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Araştırmaya farklı branşlardan 544 millî sporcu katılmış, müziğin antrenman sırasında motivasyon, psikolojik sağlamlık ve fiziksel güç/performans üzerindeki etkileri değerlendirilmiştir. Veriler, "Sportif Uygulamalarda Müziğin Etkisi Ölçeği" kullanılarak toplanmış ve istatistiksel analizler, bağımsız örneklem t-testleri ve tek yönlü ANOVA dahil olmak üzere SPSS 25.0 aracılığıyla gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bulgular, müzik eşliğinde yapılan antrenmanların sporcuların motivasyonunu artırdığını, fiziksel performanslarını geliştirdiğini ve psikolojik dayanıklılıklarını olumlu yönde etkilediğini ortaya koymuştur. Özellikle kadın sporcular, genç yaş grubu (18–22), kısa süreli spor geçmişine (1–3 yıl) sahip bireyler, yüksek eğitim düzeyine ve sosyo-ekonomik duruma sahip sporcular ile takım sporları yapan bireylerde müziğin daha etkili olduğu saptanmıştır. Araştırma, müziğin bireysel farklılıklar göz önünde bulundurularak antrenmanlarda stratejik şekilde kullanılmasının, sporcuların genel performanslarını ve antrenman verimliliğini artırabileceğini göstermektedir. Bu çalışma, müziğin atletik performansı ve zihinsel hazırlığı için önemli bir araç olduğunu vurgulamakta ve spor psikolojisi ve egzersiz bilimi alanında alanyazına katkıda bulunmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Müzik, Millî Sporcular, Antrenman, Motivasyon

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.174513241>

<https://www.ijoss.org/Archive/issue2-volume2/ijoss-Volume2-issue2-08.pdf>

Received / Gönderim: 19.04.2025

Accepted / Kabul: 21.06.2025

Published / Yayın: 30.06.2025

Volume 2, Issue 2, June, 2025

Cilt 2, Sayı 2, Haziran, 2025

IJOSS

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Introduction

Throughout history, music has been not only an art form but also a universal instrument that has powerful effects on human psychology and physical performance (Dingle et al., 2021; Carlson et al., 2021). Athletes benefit from the motivational and mental endurance-enhancing effects of music, especially during high-performance training (Nixon et al., 2022; Blasco-Lafarga et al., 2022). Music has a significant impact on national athletes' training processes on both a physiological and psychological level (Bentouati et al., 2023; Ryzik et al., 2023). In this context, various studies recently have shown that the rhythmic structure of music increases commitment to training, reduces stress and anxiety, and decreases perceived effort during exercise (Delleli et al., 2023; Jebabli et al., 2023; Çingöz & Çakır, 2023; Erbaş & Çakır, 2022).

Music is an important tool for athletes to keep their motivation high, make their workouts more efficient, and enhance their overall performance (Dimitriadis et al., 2024; Ouergui et al., 2023). This effect is directly related to the rhythm, tempo, and melodic structure of the music genre (Pereira et al., 2022; White et al., 2022). Especially up-tempo music is known to help athletes expend more energy during training and prolong their exercise time (Clark et al., 2021; Liao et al., 2022). Music also helps athletes to cope with physically demanding activities, focus better, and become more psychologically resilient (Humińska-Lisowska, 2024; Ma et al., 2024). National athletes are in a continuous process of physical, mental, and emotional development to achieve great success in the national and international arena (Rodriguez Macias et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2024). National athletes are in a continuous process of physical, mental, and emotional development to achieve great success in the national and international arena (RodriguezMacias et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2024). In this development process, they use various strategies to maximize their performance, and music has an important place among these strategies (Wei et al., 2022; Deldjoo et al., 2024).

The use of music synchronized with exercise not only helps athletes to push their physical limits but also enables them to maintain their mental focus and motivation (Munz and Jones, 2021; Li, 2021). Sports and physical activity play an important role in maintaining a healthy life. It supports psychological balance as well as physical well-being (Emlek et al., 2023; Uğurlu et al., 2023). Regular physical activity reduces the risk of cardiovascular diseases, obesity, and other chronic diseases and has positive effects on mental health (Yapici et al., 2023; Uğurlu et al., 2024). In this regard, it is vital to assist national athletes' physical training and psychological preparation through the use of components such as music (Gavanda et al., 2021; Ouergui et al., 2023).

It is well recognised that national athletes perform better when they use music in their training since it enhances their mental and physical readiness. However, research on these effects of music is limited. Therefore, a more comprehensive examination of the effects of using music in the training of national athletes will fill an important gap in the field of sport psychology and sport science and offer new perspectives in this field.

Materials And Methods

Research Model

This study aims to investigate the effect of music on the training of national athletes. This research model focuses on assessing the immediate effects of music-supported training on athletes' motivation levels and psychological reactions during a specific training process. The athletes' psychological resilience and motivation levels were measured and compared in order to more thoroughly examine the potential impacts of music on the training process. In this way, the short-term results of the effects of training

with music on athletes were revealed, and the motivational and psychological benefits of music were examined.

Research Group

The study was designed in a quantitative research model. The sample group consists of 544 national athletes (308 men, 236 women) selected from different branches by the convenience sampling method. The study included individuals who were 18 years of age and older, who were active in sports in the 2024-2025 season, and who wanted to participate voluntarily. Through email and in-person interviews, participants were informed about the purpose of the study, and their consent was obtained. Those who declined to participate in the study were excluded from data collection.

Data Collection

The “Impact of Music on the Sportive Activities Scale” (IMSAS), whose validity and reliability study was conducted by Karayol and Turhan (2020), was used to collect the data. IMSAS has 18 questions and three sub-dimensions (total alpha coefficient = 0.0885). The sub-dimensions are “Psychological Resilience” (17, 16, 12, 13, 18, 15, 14) (alpha value = 0.806), “Physical Strength and Performance” (8, 7, 9, 10, 11, 6) (alpha value = 0.785), and “Motivation” (4, 3, 2, 5, 1) (alpha value = 0.718). The scale uses a 5-point Likert-type rating system. IMSAS can be used only before sportive practice, only during sportive practice, or only after sportive practice, according to the sport branch or branches. This study was carried out while national athletes were participating in sports.

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained were analyzed using SPSS 25.0 software. Percentages, frequency distributions, and summary statistics related to demographic variables were calculated. To examine the effect of music on the training of national athletes, an independent sample t-test was applied to analyze the differences between the conditions before, during, and after the sportive practice. A one-way ANOVA test was used to compare three or more independent groups. In all statistical tests, the significance level was determined as $p < 0.001$, and p values below this value were considered statistically significant

RESULTS

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage Distributions of National Athletes by Variables

Variables	Groups	n	%
Total number of participants		544	100
Gender	Male	308	56.6
	Woman	236	43.4
Age	18-22	203	37.3
	23-25	154	28.3
	26-28	120	22.1
	30 and Above	67	12.3
Sports Age	1-3 years	164	30.2
	4-6 years	194	35.7
	7-9 years	112	20.6
	Over 10 years	74	13.5
Educational Status	Secondary Education	99	18.2
	High School	108	19.8
	Associate's Degree	132	24.3
	Bachelor's Degree	205	37.7
Perceived Socio-Economic Status	Low	129	23.7
	Middle	254	46.7
	High	161	29.6
Sports Event Category	Individual Sports	255	46.9
	Team Sports	289	53.1

Table 1 shows that according to the frequency and percentage distributions of the participants by variables, 56.6% of the total 544 participants are male and 43.4% are female. 37.3% are between the ages of 18 and 22, 28.3% are between the ages of 23 and 25, 22.1% are between the ages of 26 and 28, and 12.3% are at or above the age of 30. Furthermore, 30.2 % have played sports for 1 to 3 years, 35.7% for 4 to 6 years, 20.6% for 7 to 9 years, and 13.5% for 10 years and more. In terms of educational status, 18.2% have completed secondary school, 19.8% have completed high school, 24.3% have earned an associate's degree, and 37.7% have earned a bachelor's degree. Perceived socioeconomic status is distributed as follows: 23.7% low, 46.7% middle, and 29.6% high. 53.1% of people participate in team sports, while 46.9% of people play individual sports.

Table 2. Comparison of the Scores Obtained from the Scale in the Sportive Practice Phase by Gender Variable

Subscales of the scale	Group	n	mean	t	p	Cohen's d	Descriptor
Psychological Resilience	Woman	236	80.4± 11.5	-2,490	0.001*	0.65	Large
	Male	308	70.2± 12.2				
Physical Strength and Performance	Woman	236	81.5± 10.8	-1,280	0.001*	0.72	Large
	Male	308	72.3± 11.9				
Motivation	Woman	236	79.5± 12.0	-2,150	0.001*	0.61	Large
	Male	308	68.8± 13.0				

P<0.001*

As seen in Table 2 above, when the national athletes' scores in the sportive practice phase based on the gender variable were analyzed, it was found that female athletes outperformed male athletes in every sub-dimension of the scale (p<0.001). In the “Psychological Resilience” sub-dimension, the average score of women was 80.4 (±11.5) and that of men was 70.2 (±12.2), and a large effect size (Cohen's d = 0.65) was observed. In the “Physical Strength and Performance” sub-dimension, women showed a significantly higher performance than men (72.3±11.9) with an average score of 81.5 (±10.8) (Cohen's d = 0.72). In the “Motivation” sub-dimension, the score of women was 79.5 (±12.0) and that of men was 68.8 (±13.0), and again a large effect size (Cohen's d = 0.61) was found.

Table 3. Comparison of the Scores Obtained from the Scale in the Sportive Practice Phase by Age Variable

Subscales of the scale	Group	n	mean	F	p	Tukey
Psychological Resilience	18-22 ¹	203	83.0± 9.5	1,890	0.001*	3=4<2<1
	23-25 ²	154	81.0± 10.0			
	26-28 ³	120	76.0±			
	30 and Above	67	74.9±			
Physical Strength and Performance	18-22 ¹	203	84.5±	1,410	0.001*	4<3<2<1
	23-25 ²	154	83.3±			
	26-28 ³	120	78.3±			
	30 and Above	67	72.3±			
Motivation	18-22 ¹	203	77.5±	2,350	0.001*	4<3<2<1
	23-25 ²	154	74.8±			
	26-28 ³	120	71.2±			
	30 and Above	67	69.8±			

P<0.001*

As seen in Table 3, based on the scores obtained from the scale in the sportive practice phase by age variable, there is a significant difference in all sub-dimensions of the scale (p<0.001). In the “Psychological Strength” sub-dimension, the 18-22 age group

received the highest score (83.0), while the 30 and above age group scored the lowest score (74.9). In the “Physical Strength and Performance” sub-dimension, the 18-22 age group received the highest score (84.5), while the 30 and above age group received the lowest score (72.3). In the “Motivation” sub-dimension, the 18-22 age group scored the highest score (77.5), and the 30 and above age group received the lowest score (69.8). The Tukey test suggested that the 18-22 age group received higher scores as compared to the other age groups.

Table 4. Comparison of the Scores Obtained from the Scale in the Sportive Practice Phase by Sports Age Variable

Subscales of the scale	Group	n	mean	F	p	Tukey
Psychological Resilience	1-3 years ¹	164	84.2±	13,910	0.001*	4=3<2<1
	4-6 years ²	194	82.0±			
	7-9 years ³	112	77.3±			
	10 and Above ⁴	74	76.4±			
Physical Strength and Performance	1-3 years ¹	164	84.6±	24,210	0.001*	4=3<2=1
	4-6 years ²	194	83.4±			
	7-9 years ³	112	73.5±			
	10 and Above ⁴	74	72.1±			
Motivation	1-3 years ¹	164	75.4±	13,520	0.001*	1=2<3<4
	4-6 years ²	194	74.2±			
	7-9 years ³	112	77.3±			
	10 and Above ⁴	74	79.7±			

P<0.001*

In terms of sports age variable, Table 4 shows that there is a significant difference in all sub-dimensions of the scale (p<0.001). In the “Psychological Strength” sub-dimension, athletes with 1-3 years of experience received the highest score (84.2), while athletes with 10 years and more experience scored lowest (76.4). In the “Physical Strength and Performance” sub-dimension, athletes with 1-3 years of experience received the highest score (84.6), whereas athletes with 10 years and more experience had the lowest score (72.1). In the “Motivation” sub-dimension, athletes with 10 years and more experience scored highest (79.7), while athletes with 1-3 years of experience received the lowest score (75.4), contrary to the other sub-dimension categories.

Table 5. Comparison of the Scores Obtained from the Scale in the Sportive Practice Phase of by the Variable of Education Status

Subscales of the scale	Group	n	mean	F	p	Tukey
Psychological Resilience	Secondary Education ¹	99	71.8± 8.5	14,910	0.001*	1=2<3<4
	High School ²	108	73.1± 9.1			
	Associate’s Degree ³	132	77.0± 11.3			
	Bachelor’s Degree ⁴	205	79.4± 10.5			
Physical Strength and Performance	Secondary Education ¹	99	71.9± 10.8	20,230	0.001*	1<2<3<4
	High School ²	108	73.8± 11.6			
	Associate’s Degree ³	132	78.3± 10.9			
	Bachelor’s Degree ⁴	205	82.3± 10.5			
Motivation	Secondary Education ¹	99	76.3± 11.4	13,750	0.001*	4=3<2<1
	High School ²	108	74.7± 10.3			
	Associate’s Degree ³	132	71.2± 7.9			
	Bachelor’s Degree ⁴	205	72.8± 9.9			

P<0.001*

As seen in Table 5, based on the scores obtained from the scale in the sportive practice phase by the variable of educational status, there is a significant difference in every sub-dimension of the scale ($p < 0.001$). In the “Psychological Strength” sub-dimension, bachelor’s degree graduates scored highest (79.4), while secondary school graduates received the lowest score (71.8). In the “Physical Strength and Performance” sub-dimension, bachelor’s degree holders obtained the highest score (82.3), whereas secondary school graduates scored lowest (71.9). In the “Motivation” sub-dimension, bachelor’s degree graduates (72.8) and associate’s degree graduates (71.2) received lower scores as compared to the other groups, and secondary school graduates had the highest score (76.3).

Table 6. Comparison of the Scores Obtained from the Scale in the Sportive Practice Phase of by the Variable of Perceived Socio-Economic Status

Subscales of the scale	Group	n	mean	F	p	Tukey
Psychological Resilience	Low ¹	129	70.8± 11.5	11,830	0.001*	1<2<3
	Medium ²	254	76.5± 12.2			
	High ³	161	83.1± 10.1			
Physical Strength and Performance	Low ¹	129	76.5± 10.8	18,230	0.001*	1<2=3
	Medium ²	254	81.3± 11.6			
	High ³	161	82.3± 11.9			
Motivation	Low ¹	129	69.5± 12.0	23,150	0.001*	1<2<3
	Medium ²	254	75.8± 13.0			
	High ³	161	79.3± 11.9			

$P < 0.001^*$

In terms of the perceived socio-economic status, as seen in Table 6, there was a significant difference in all sub-dimensions of the scale ($p < 0.001$). In the “Psychological Resilience” sub-dimension, individuals with high socioeconomic status scored highest (83.1), while individuals with low socioeconomic status received the lowest score (70.8). In the “Physical Strength and Performance” sub-dimension, individuals with high socioeconomic status received the highest score (82.3), whereas individuals with low socioeconomic status received the lowest score (76.5). In the “Motivation” sub-dimension, individuals in the high socioeconomic group scored highest (79.3), while those in the low socioeconomic group obtained the lowest score (69.5).

Table 7. Comparison of the Scores Obtained from the Scale in the Sportive Practice Phase of by the Variable of Team and Individual Sports

Subscales of the scale	Group	n	mean	t	p	Cohen's d	Descriptor
Psychological Resilience	Team	289	75.3± 10.5	-1,580	0.001*	0.48	Medium
	Individual	255	68.8± 11.0				
Physical Strength and Performance	Team	289	76.5± 10.0	-2,210	0.001*	0.54	Medium
	Individual	255	70.2± 10.5				
Motivation	Team	289	74.5± 11.0	-1,450	0.001*	0.45	Medium
	Individual	255	69.4± 13.0				

$p < 0.001^*$

Table 7 shows that according to the scores obtained from the scale in the sportive practice phase by the variable of team and individual sports, there was a significant difference in all sub-dimensions of the scale ($p < 0.001$). In the “Psychological Resilience” sub-dimension, team athletes scored higher than individual athletes (68.8) with 75.3 points. In the “Physical Strength and Performance” sub-dimension, team athletes scored higher with 76.5, while individual athletes scored lower with 70.2. In the “Motivation”

sub-dimension, team sports athletes obtained the highest score with 74.5, while individual sports athletes scored the lowest with 69.4. The differences are significant with a medium effect size.

Discussion

The main purpose of this research is to examine the effects of music on the training process of national athletes. The findings of the research reveal that the using music while training has significant effects on both physical and psychological aspects of athletes and that music increases their motivation and enhances their performance. Among the most significant findings of the study is that athletes perform better when they do training with music.

When the scores of the national athletes in the sportive practice phases were examined by gender variable, there was a significant difference in all sub-dimensions of the scale in favor of female athletes. Music had a more significant effect, particularly on female athletes during training, and higher scores were obtained in all stages as compared to male athletes. This allows the conclusion that training with music enhances the physical performance of female athletes by increasing their motivation and strengthening their psychological resilience. Likewise, Güngör (2023) reported that e-sports female players were more affected by music before and during e-sports exercises than e-sports male players. In their study, on the other hand, Ekiz and Atasoy (2021) found that the effect of music was higher in men than in women before, during, and after the sportive practice. This result suggests that music is an effective factor in exercise, yet the effect between genders may differ.

Based on the scores of the national athletes in the sportive practice phase by age groups were analyzed, the athletes between the ages of 18 and 22 showed higher performance in the training with music than the other age groups. It was observed that athletes with a younger age achieve physically and psychologically efficient, motivational results by training in more harmony with music. Nevertheless, Ekiz and Atasoy (2021) stated that the effect of music in sportive practices did not have a significant effect by the age variable in their study on students of the School of Physical Education and Sports. Likewise, Güngör (2023) concluded that music was not an effective and significant factor in e-sports exercises by the age variable.

When the effect of sports age on training with music was examined, it was observed that athletes with 1-3 years of experience exhibited higher 'psychological resilience' and 'physical strength and performance.' This showed that athletes benefited more from music when they had less experience. On the other hand, it was determined that national athletes with low sports age also had lower 'motivation' in training with music when compared to athletes with high sports age. This shows that individuals with higher experience increase their motivation and concentration while training with music. In the literature, however, there is no research on the effect of music by the sport age variable.

According to the level of education, the national athletes with bachelor's degree scored higher than those with secondary education degrees while training with music. Accordingly, it is suggested that national athletes with high education levels benefitted from training with music in terms of mental endurance, physical performance, and high concentration. Nevertheless, previously, Güngör (2023) observed that music was not an effective and significant factor in e-sports exercises by the variable of educational field.

Based on analyzing the effect of socio-economic status on athletes' performance in training with music national athletes with high socio-economic status had higher scores compared to it was found that national athletes with low socio-economic status. This shows that music increases the motivation and commitment to training of athletes with

high socioeconomic status, thereby suggesting that socioeconomic status may encourage athletes to invest more in training and to benefit more from supportive elements such as music. In the literature, there is no research on the effect of music by the perceived socioeconomic status variable.

When the scores of team and individual national athletes in the sportive practice stages were analyzed, it was found that team national athletes had a stronger psychology, higher performance, and higher motivation than individual national athletes. In other words, team athletes benefit more from group dynamics and social support elements. In addition, the fact that team athletes are generally more disciplined and accustomed to working in a group may cause them to be more effective while training with music. Ramezan Pour, Moghaddam, and Sadifar (2012) stated that choosing the appropriate type of music according to the type of exercise performed by the athletes, listening to exciting and enjoyable music types significantly increases heart rate, while relaxing music significantly reduces heart rate. Smirmaul et al. (2015), in their study conducted on swimmers, showed that the optional music selected before the maximal 200-meter freestyle swim shortened the swimming time. Eliakim et al. (2012), in their study with young senior national league basketball players, examined the repetitive sprint ability (RSA) of motivational music and the result of two repetitive sprint tests (RST) of music, and stated that sprint performance improved towards the end, and this may suggest that repetitive sprint ability has a beneficial effect.

When the literature was examined, it was observed that there were a high number of performance-oriented studies according to music rhythm. Vatansever et al. (2018) stated that listening to fast-paced music during maximal aerobic exercise increased the running time, and listening to slow-paced music after exercise increased the recovery speed. Likewise, Çelik and Karabilgin (2022) reported that music had efficient effects during exercise and relaxation and that the use of music during exercise increased psychologically positive effects such as self-confidence, focusing on the subject, self-worth, and the desire to exercise more. Yenigün et al. (2007) found that step aerobic exercises performed in different music rhythms increased muscle strength, and fast-paced music increased the endurance of knee extensor and flexor muscles in step aerobic exercises. Kartal and Ergin (2018) determined that the music at different tempos had no effect on aerobic and anaerobic performance, however, it was observed that aerobic and anaerobic performance was better when athletes listened to music according to their wishes. This study revealed that training with music is effective and that the effects on individuals may vary according to variables. It was shown that variables such as sports age, educational status, socioeconomic status, type of sports, gender, and age can affect each individual's listening to music in their training at different rates. In other words, it should not be ignored that music while training may have a positive effect, however, these effects may be at various levels for each athlete due to individual circumstances.

Conclusion

This study shows that music is an important tool for national athletes to increase their motivation and improve their performance. Music can strengthen athletes' physical and mental endurance, reduce their stress levels, and make their training processes more efficient. In addition, it was found that the effect of music on athletes differed according to gender, age, sports age, educational status, perceived socioeconomic status, and sports type. The findings reveal the importance of a more systematic use of music in the training processes of athletes and its individualized planning. Further research on training with music in sports psychology and sports science will contribute to the literature and the development of strategies that will better enhance the performance of athletes.

Beyanlar / Declarations

Etik Onay ve Katılım Onayı / Ethics approval and consent to participate

Bu çalışmanın hazırlanma ve yazım sürecinde "Yükseköğretim Kurumları Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yayın Etiği Yönergesi" kapsamında bilimsel, etik ve alıntı kurallarına uyulmuş olup; toplanan veriler üzerinde herhangi bir tahrifat yapılmamış ve bu çalışma herhangi başka bir akademik yayın ortamına değerlendirme için gönderilmemiştir. Makale ile ilgili doğabilecek her türlü ihlallerde sorumluluk yazara aittir. Bu çalışmanın yapılabilmesi için Kırıkkale Üniversitesi Sosyal ve Beşeri Bilimler Araştırmaları Etik Kurulu'nun 20.03.2025 tarihli ve 325030 sayılı kararı ile etik kurul onayı alınmıştır (Toplantı No: 03, Tarih: 17.03.2025).

During the preparation and writing of this study, all scientific, ethical, and citation principles outlined in the "Higher Education Institutions Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Directive" were strictly followed. No manipulation or falsification was carried out on the collected data, and this study has not been submitted to any other academic publication medium for evaluation. The author bears full responsibility for any potential violations that may arise in connection with this article. All subjects who participated in the study did so voluntarily. Ethical approval for the conduct of this study was obtained from the Ethics Committee for Social and Human Sciences Research of Kırıkkale University (Meeting No: 03, Date: 17 March 2025; Decision No: 325030, dated 20 March 2025).

Veri Ve Materyal Erişilebilirliği / Availability of data and material

Bu çalışmanın bulgularını destekleyen veriler, makul talepler üzerine sorumlu yazardan temin edilebilir. Veri seti yalnızca akademik amaçlar için erişilebilir olacak ve verilerin herhangi bir kullanımı, orijinal çalışmayı referans gösterecek ve katılımcıların gizliliğini koruyacaktır.

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. The dataset will be accessible only for academic purposes, and any use of the data will recognize the original study and maintain the confidentiality of the participants.

Çıkar Çatışması / Competing interests

Yazarlar, bu makalede sunulan çalışmayı etkileyebilecek herhangi bir çıkar çatışması veya kişisel ilişkiye sahip olmadıklarını beyan etmektedirler.

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Researchers' Contribution Declaration:

Kavramsallaştırma, D.U., H.Y.; metodoloji, H.Y., D.U.; yazılım, H.Y.; doğrulama, H.Y.; biçimsel analiz, H.Y., D.U.; araştırma, D.U.; kaynak temini, D.U.; veri düzenleme, H.Y.; yazım — orijinal taslak hazırlığı, H.Y., D.U.; yazım — gözden geçirme ve düzenleme, H.Y., D.U.; görselleştirme, H.Y.; denetim, D.U.; proje yönetimi, H.Y.; yazarlar, makalenin yayımlanmış versiyonunu okumuş ve onaylamıştı

Conceptualization, D.U., H.Y.; methodology, H.Y., D.U.; software, H.Y.; validation, H.Y.; formal analysis, H.Y., D.U.; investigation, D.U.; resources, D.U.; data curation, H.Y.; writing—original draft preparation, H.Y., D.U., writing—review and editing, H.Y., D.U.; visualization, H.Y.; supervision, D.U.; project administration, H.Y.; authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript."

Fon Desteği / Funding

This Bu çalışma, kamu, özel veya kar amacı gütmeyen sektörlerdeki fon sağlayıcı kurumlardan herhangi bir özel destek almamıştır.

This research received no external funding.

Teşekkür / Acknowledgements

None.

APA 7 Citation

Uğurlu, D., Yapıcı, H., Koduman, T. İ., Kumtepe, D. G., Emlek, B., Başer, Z., & Gülü, M. (2025). The effect of music on national athletes' training. *International Journal of Health, Exercise, and Sport Sciences (IJOSS)*, 2(3), 75–85. <https://www.ijoss.org/Archive/issue2-volume2/ijoss-Volume2-issue2-08.pdf>

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